

The role of Tahfidzul Quran Program to Improve the Student Learning Outcomes in 7th Grade of Mts Nurul Iman Pomalaa District

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Abstract

Memorizing the Qur'an is a way to remember verse by verse in the Qur'an, including fluency in reciting and the correctness of recitation, all of which must be memorized perfectly and completely. Based on several relevant studies regarding memorizing the Qur'an, it shows that there is a correlation for students who memorize the Qur'an in increasing their Intelligence Quotient.

MTs Nurul Iman at Pomalaa subdistrict, implements the program of Tahfidzul Quran as the prime program of school which is expected to increase and build the spirituality of the students. However, the authors have conducted research on the role of the tahfidzul Quran program in improving student learning outcomes at MTs Nurul Iman, Pomalaa District. to find out whether it is true that the Qur'an has a role in improving student learning outcomes. The results showed that students who took part in the tahfidzul Qur'an program experienced an improvement in aspects both in terms of changes in morals and behavior, as well as from the aspect of improving their learning outcomes. Because there are some students who initially before joining the tahfidzul Qur'an program the percentage of learning outcomes was at the standard value. After participating in the tahfidz program, the percentage of learning outcomes is able to compete with children who are ranked in the top 10.

Keywords: Tahfidzul Quran, Learning Outcomes, Students.

A. Preface

The essence of the Qur'an has a great influence on advancing world civilization whose scope is in accordance with applicable humanitarian norms. This will have a good impact on the millennial generation when they are able to learn, read, understand, memorize and even apply the values contained in the Qur'an.

Memorizing the Qur'an is a suggestion from the Prophet Muhammad SAW. to make it easier to keep it, this is commonly known as the Talaqqi method. The Talaqqi method is a way of learning to teach the Qur'an from the Prophet to his companions and then from them to the next generation even today. The method of memorizing the Qur'an by the Prophet's method makes it easier to realize Qur'anic people who are able to memorize the Qur'an properly and correctly as well as practice its contents in everyday life.¹

Someone who memorizes the Qur'an and understands the meaning of the text also the universal meaning contained in it, then he really knows his God and knows the purpose and nature of life that is written secretly in it.² Academics and specialists agree that memorizing the Qur'an has a good effect on the intelligence and basic skills of students so that it can improve students' academic achievement. Abdullah Subaih, Professor of Psychology at Imam Muhammad Bin Su'ud al-Islamiyah University in Riyadh, appealed to students to take guidance on memorizing the Qur'an. He also emphasized that memorizing the Qur'an can help concentration and conditions for obtaining blessed knowledge.³

The Qur'an which has this extraordinary miracle isn't only able to provide intelligence to the human brain, but also able to provide peace and tranquility for people who always read and even

¹Abdul Qawi, "Peningkatan Prestasi Belajar Hafalan Al-Qur'an Melalui Metode Talaqqi di MTs.N Gampong Teungoh Aceh Utara", *Jurnal Ilmiah Islam Futura*, Vol. XVI. Nomor 2, 2017, p. 270.

²Sholah Abdul Fatah al-Kholidi, *Membedah Al-Qur'an Versi Al-Qur'an*, (Cet. I; Surabaya: Pustaka Progressif, 1997), p. 33.

³ Risnawati Pasaribu, "Pengaruh Hafalan Al-Qur'an Terhadap Kedisiplinan Belajar Dan Prestasi Belajar Pada Siswa SD Muhammadiyah Suronatan Yogyakarta", *Jurnal Bimbingan Dan Konseling*, Vol. II. Nomor 2, 2018, hlm. 175.

memorize it.⁴ It is not surprising that students who often read and even memorize the Qur'an will have average grade/higher IQ than the students who rarely read the Qur'an. Because of the process that the student's brain will get used to memorizing something that is read and heard. This also affects the speed of the child's brain in processing the subjects it receives in formal education.⁵

MTs Nurul Iman Pomalaa is one of the Madrasah Tsanawiyah which is located in Kumoro Village, Pomalaa District, Kolaka Regency as a formal educational institution that provides opportunities for students to develop their own talents but madrasahs still provide facilities to their students. one of them is coaching to memorize the Qur'an 30 juz.

Based on first observation, it showed that there were 64 students who started memorizing the Qur'an at MTs Nurul Iman Pomalaa from various grade levels, from class VII (Seven) to Class IX (Nine).⁶ This shows that the students' interest in memorizing the Qur'an at MTs Nurul Iman Pomalaa is very large. Therefore, schools, parents and the community must provide their support. Thus, is there any effects from the Tahfidzul Qur'an program in improving student learning outcomes?.

B. Research Results

MTs Nurul Iman Pomalaa was founded in 1983. It was motivated by the anxiety of Islamic religious leaders in Pomalaa District, especially religious leaders at the Antam Pomalaa Complex about the behavior and moral conditions of Islamic youth which were far from Islamic values and teachings. Based on this, a Foundation was formed with the name Nurul Iman Islamic Education Foundation (YAPNI) which was then intended to establish a religion-based educational institution, which was initiated by establishing Diniyah Awaliyah and Diniyah Wustha, then along with the changing times it developed into Madrasah Tsanawiyah Nurul Iman Pomalaa.

⁴ Sofyan Rofi, "Analisis Perbedaan Hasil Belajar Siswa Mengikuti Program Tahfidz AlQur'an (Studi Kasus di SMP Muhammadiyah 9 Watukebo Jember)", *Jurnal Pendidikan Agama Islam*, Vol. II. Nomor 1, 2019, hlm. 2.

⁵ Mustofa Kamal, "Pengaruh Pelaksanaan Program Menghafal Al-Qur'an Terhadap Prestasi Belajar Siswa", *Jurnal Pendidikan Islam*, Vol. VI. Nomor 2, 2017, hlm. 16.

⁶ Interview Result to Arfan Junaid, (Headmaster MTs. Nurul Iman Kecamatan Pomalaa), at 06 Oct 2020.

a. The process and application of the Qur'an memorization program for students at MTs Nurul Iman Pomalaa.

The Qur'an tahfidz program at MTs Nurul Iman Pomalaa is not an obligation for all students and is only an option for students to improve the talents that exist within them. For students who are included in the Tahfidz Qur'an program, they are required to stay at the Tahfidz house as an effort to make it easier for Tahfidz teachers to coordinate students who memorize the Qur'an and can make it easier for students who have a house far from the school.

Before start to memorize the Qur'an, it is required to improve the tajwid at first as an effort to improve the reading and memorization of the Qur'an of students. While the method used by students in memorizing the Qur'an is the memorization method used in general, namely memorization, then confronted with the tahfidz teacher after that murajaah to further strengthen memorization.

To find out the extent of success in achieving the implementation of the tahfidzul Qur'an program, it is very necessary to have an evaluation. MTs Nurul Iman Pomalaa held an evaluation of the implementation of the Qur'an tahfidz program when there were students who had memorized 5, 10, 15, 20, 25 or even 30 juz. the process of tahfidzul Qur'an activities at MTs Nurul Iman Pomalaa through several structured stages to be able to memorize 30 Juz of the Qur'an. The students are selected to be able to memorize and then stabilize recitation after that run the target of memorization and murajaah and conduct a gradual evaluation as a form of strengthening the memorization of the Qur'an of students. So that the purpose of the Qur'an tahfidz program can be realized and then there are outputs produced.

b) Learning outcomes of students in the tahfidz program

Apart from memorizing the Qur'an which is expected by parents and teachers from the tahfidz Qur'an program of students. Changes in behavior and even learning outcomes are also the wishes of

parents and teachers. Because they believe that the Qur'an can provide intellectual intelligence, emotional intelligence and spiritual intelligence.

The existence of the tahfidz program in the madrasa is very helpful for parents and teachers, especially teachers who teach in the religious field. For example, the subjects of Aqidah Akhlaq, Al-Qur'an Hadith and so on. It's not just classroom teachers who say that students who take part in the tahfidz program have superior achievements, but Amirullah Majid as the head of the Madrasah said so.

From the results of the interviews, it can be shown that students who take part in the tahfidzul Qur'an program have many very significant changes both in the learning process, the practice of worship and changes in behavior in their daily lives. The learning outcomes of students who take part in the tahfidz program are more satisfying than before memorizing the Qur'an. Therefore, the miracle of the verses of the Koran that have been memorized by students so as to provide positive stimuli unconsciously to those who memorize them. This is also in line with what is known together that the Qur'an is the greatest miracle of the Prophet Muhammad SAW.

c). Factors that affect student learning outcomes in the Qur'an tahfidz program

All processes to get maximum results, especially regarding learning problems, cannot be separated from the factors that influence it. There are 2 dominant factors that can affect student learning outcomes, namely supporting and inhibiting factors. The supporting factors are:

1. Teachers' Role

Teachers have a very important role in the development of student learning. The four competencies that must be possessed by a teacher are: pedagogic competence, personality competence, social competence and professional competence.

2. Parents' Support

Parents also have an important role in the level of success of students in the learning process. In addition to praying for their children in success, parents must also provide motivation, spirit and examples to their children so that they feel cared for which then stimulates their brain and feelings to always learn and learn.

3. Tahfidz Program

One of the flagship programs in MTs Nurul Iman Pomalaa is the Qur'an tahfidz program which can improve student learning outcomes because their discipline and mentality have been trained so well by their tahfidz teachers. The Tahfidzul Qur'an program has an important role in improving student learning outcomes at MTs Nurul Iman Pomalaa, this is proven by the results of the documentation that has been collected by researchers, namely the average value of students from class VII semesters 1 and 2, as follows:

Table 4.3 the average values of students class VII (Semester I)

MTs Nurul Iman Pomalaa 2019/2020

No.	Students' Name	Average Score	Participants Program	Non-Participants Program
1	Abdul Awwab Asdar	80.5	√	
2	Abdul Azhim Asdar	82	√	
3	Andi Arma Dewi	76.5		√
4	Andita Suryana	77		√
5	Annisa	87.5	√	
6	Dirga Zulkarnaen AS.	74.5		√
7	Faiqah Muthiah	76		√

8	Friska Nur Pratiwi	80		√
9	Muh. Fajrin Ramadhan	90.5	√	
10	Muhammad Irvan	79.5		√
11	Muhammad Putra Alfiansyah	77.5		√
12	Muhammad Rivaldhy K.	77		√
14	Muhammad Rifky Suwardi	75		√
15	Mutiara Rochmadi	84.5		√
16	Nabila	79		√
17	Nabila Nurul Hidayah	83	√	
18	Nensih Pratiwi	80.5		√
19	Nur Aisyahyani	86		√
20	Nur Dita Rahmayani	82.5	√	
21	Nuraisyah	80		√
22	Putri Asih Nadatiara	85		√
23	Rahmah	81.5	√	
24	Rangga Saputra	78		√
25	Rifaldi	84.5	√	
26	Riska Amelia	80		√
27	Rizky Handika Prayuda	88.5		√
28	Saskia	79.5		√
29	Siti Nur Halima	89		√
30	Sophan Ardiansyah	70		√
31	Wilda	76		√
32	Windha Arthamevia M	82.5		√

33	Zidane Al-Fateh Pratama	79		√
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Sumber : homeroom Archives of Class VII semester 1 Year 2019-2020

Table 4.3 the average values of students class VII (Semester II)

MTs Nurul Iman Pomalaa 2019/2020

No.	Students' Name	Average Score	Participants Program	Non-Participants Program
1	Abdul Awwab Asdar	82.5	√	
2	Abdul Azhim Asdar	81	√	
3	Andi Arma Dewi	77		√
4	Andita Suryana	75		√
5	Annisa	89	√	
6	Dirga Zulkarnaen AS.	76		√
7	Faiqah Muthiah	75.5		√
8	Friska Nur Pratiwi	79		√
9	Muh. Fajrin Ramadhan	90	√	

10	Muhammad Irvan	78		√
11	Muhammad Putra Alfiansyah	75.5		√
12	Muhammad Rivaldhy K.	77		√
14	Muhammad Rifky Suwardi	78		√
15	Mutiara Rochmadi	85		√

16	Nabila	80		√
17	Nabila Nurul Hidayah	85.5	√	
18	Nensih Pratiwi	82		√
19	Nur Aisyahyani	84.5		√
20	Nur Dita Rahmayani	80.5	√	
21	Nuraisyah	83		√
22	Putri Asih Nadatiara	86.5		√
23	Rahmah	85.5	√	
24	Rangga Saputra	76.5		√
25	Rifaldi	85.5	√	
26	Riska Amelia	80.5		√
27	Rizky Handika Prayuda	87		√
28	Saskia	82.5		√
29	Siti Nur Halima	88.5		√
30	Sophan Ardiansyah	73		√
31	Wilda	73.5		√
32	Windha Arthamevia M	84.5		√
33	Zidane Al-Fateh Pratama	78.5		√

Sumber : homeroom Archives of Class VII semester II Year 2019-2020

In addition to supporting factors, there are also inhibiting factors from student learning outcomes who participate in the Qur'an tahfidz program, namely the level of intelligence of students who are different, some are faster in understanding and some may even have repeated it but have not understood it.

Conclusion

The Qur'an tahfidz program is an effort to assist educators in educating students at MTs Nurul Iman, Pomalaa District. The Tahfidz program is also one of the flagship programs of MTs Nurul Iman, Pomalaa District. The students who take part in the tahfidz program continue to carry out formal schooling as usual, but they are required to stay at the tahfidz house which has been prepared by MTs Nurul Iman Pomalaa so that the memorization process is easier for the tahfidz teacher to reach.

The tahfidz program at MTs Nurul Iman, Pomalaa District, has an extraordinary role in overhauling student learning outcomes. More than that, the tahfidz program can also change the behavior of students who were previously uncivilized, now almost 180 degrees from before. This is based on the students' habits in hearing and memorizing the Qur'an almost every day, without realizing it also trains students to do and speak well.

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